

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-XV. Synthesis of Thiazolidinones from Mono- and Di-Substituted Thioureas Possessing Alicyclic and Heterocyclic Substituents

(Miss) J. SAHU, S. S. MEHBR, S. NAIK

and

A. NAYAK

Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University,
Jyoti Vihar-768 019

Manuscript received 12 August 1983, revised 17 April 1984,
accepted 18 January 1985

ALTHOUGH several derivatives of thiazolidinones having versatile pharmaceutical and industrial values have been reported^{1,2}, the thiazolidinones having alicyclic substituents are not known. In continuation of our previous studies³ a few new thiazolidinones possessing alicyclic and heterocyclic substituents, such as 2-cyclo-alkylimino-4-thiazolidinones (2a-c; R=H), 2-[2'-phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3']-4-thiazolidinone (2d), 2-(acridyl-9) imino-4-thiazolidinones (2e) have been reported here. These were synthesised from their respective thioureas by reacting with monochloroacetic acid in the presence of anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol. The thioureas were obtained by the reaction of benzoylthiocyanate with the amines and subsequent hydrolysis of the reaction products (Scheme 1).

- a Q=Cyclopentyl, R=H
b Q=Cyclohexyl, R=H
c Q=Cycloheptyl, R=H
d Q=3(2-Phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin)
e Q=Acridyl-9, R=H
f R=Cyclopentyl, Q=Phenyl
g R=Cyclohexyl, Q=Phenyl
h R=Cycloheptyl, Q=Phenyl
i Q=2-Phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin, R=Phenyl
j Q=Acridyl-9, R=Phenyl
k Q=Pyrimidin, R=Phenyl

1. ClCH_2COOH , NaOAC, EtOH; 2. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CHO}$, HOAC, NaOAC; 3. Br_2 , HOAC; 4. NaNO_2 , HCl, sulphanilamide; 5. Formalin, secondary amines.

Scheme 1

The ir spectra of the thiazolidinone (2b; R=H) gave weak band at 2920 cm^{-1} and strong sharp band at 1735 cm^{-1} corresponding to CH_2 and C=O stretches, respectively, whereas its benzylidene derivative (3b; R=H) gave a strong sharp band at 1685 cm^{-1} and the band in the region 2900 cm^{-1} was absent. The bathochromic shift for the carbonyl absorption is due to the conjugation of the exomethylene group. The hypsochromic shift in carbonyl stretch (1700 cm^{-1}) of its dibromo compound (4b; R=H) indicating saturation of the exocyclic double bond also confirmed the structures.

Thiazolidinones (2 f-k; R= C_6H_5) were obtained from the disubstituted thioureas (1; R= C_6H_5) following the procedure adopted in the case of (2a-c). These thioureas were synthesised by refluxing various amines with phenylisothiocyanate. Since the thiol form of thiourea is responsible for the formation of thiazolidinones, two products, 7 and 8 might be obtained (Scheme 2). The assignment of the structure was confirmed from its hydrolysis with ethanolic HCl. The compound with structure 7 would give the 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinone (9) along with the original amino compound, whereas the compound with structure 8 would give aniline and 3-substituted-2,4-thiazolidinone (10).

Scheme 2

When the hydrolysis of the compound obtained from the reaction of 1 (Q=2-phenyl-imidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3; R= C_6H_5) and monochloroacetic acid was carried out, 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinone (9, m.p. 200° , lit.⁴ $200-201^\circ$) along with 2-phenyl-3-aminoimidazo[1,2-a]pyridine (m.p. 200°) were obtained. Similar hydrolysis of the compound from 1 (Q=cyclohexyl; R= C_6H_5) and monochloroacetic acid furnished aniline and 3-cyclohexyl-2,4-thiazolidinone (10; Q=cyclohexyl). Thus in an unsymmetrical thiourea the thiolisation appears to occur from the NH group adjacent to the substituent having unsaturation.

The disubstituted thiazolidinones were also condensed with benzaldehyde to furnish the benzylidene derivatives. Since both types of thiazolidinones possess active methylene groups several aminoalkyl derivatives and sulphonamidophenylazo derivatives were prepared with a view to evaluate their pesticidal activities.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir

spectra were taken on KBr disc in Perkin Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

3-Amino-2-arylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridine were prepared by the reaction of 2-aminopyridine and bisulphite addition product of aryl aldehydes in the presence of potassium cyanide according to Thaker, *et al*⁵. 9-Aminoacridine was prepared by the cyclisation of *N*-phenylanthranilic acid with concentrated H_2SO_4 according to the reported procedure⁶.

Cyclopentylthiourea (1a): To a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (3.8 g, 0.05 M) in dry acetone (25 ml) was added benzoylchloride (7 g, 0.5 M) dropwise with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 0.5 h. To it was added a solution of cyclopentylamine (4.25 ml, 0.5 M) in dry acetone (15 ml) with stirring at such a rate that the solution refluxed gently. The content were poured into cold water and the resulting heavy mass filtered and heated with aqueous sodium hydroxide (50 ml, 10%). The alkali soluble fragment was made acidic by adding concentrated HCl in cold, made just alkaline with ammonia and left overnight. The resulting solid (3.1 g, 43%) was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 164° (Found : S, 22.12. $C_6H_{12}N_2S$ requires S, 22.21%).

Cyclohexylthiourea (1b) (40%), m.p. 162° (Found : S, 20.06. $C_7H_{14}N_2S$ requires S, 20.25%); **2-phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridino-3-thiourea (1d)** (50%) m.p. 208° (Found : S, 11.92. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$ requires S, 11.94%); and **(acridyl-9)thiourea (1e)** (45%), m.p. 160° (Found : S, 11.42. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S$ requires S, 12.60%) were prepared by following the above general procedure.

***N*₁-Cyclopentyl-*N*₂-phenylthiocarbamide (1f) :** A solution of cyclopentylamine (0.85 g, 0.1 M) and phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g, 0.01 M) in rectified spirit was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. After cooling a colourless precipitate was filtered and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 114° (Found : S, 14.36. $C_{13}H_{16}N_2S$ requires S, 14.5%).

***N*₁-Cyclohexyl-*N*₂-phenylthiocarbamide (1g)**, m.p. 147° (Found : S, 13.35. $C_{13}H_{16}N_2S$ requires S, 13.60%); ν_{max} 3240 (NH), 1200, 1150, 1110 cm^{-1} ; ***N*₁-cycloheptyl-*N*₂-phenylthiocarbamide (1h)**, m.p. 120° (Found : S, 12.58. $C_{14}H_{20}N_2S$ requires S, 12.90%); ***N*¹-phenyl-*N*²-(2'-phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3-thiocarbamide (1i)**, m.p. 208° (Found : S, 9.27. $C_{20}H_{16}N_4S$ requires S, 9.30%); ***N*¹-phenyl-*N*²-(acridyl-9) thiocarbamide (1j)**, m.p. 191° (Found : S, 9.48. $C_{20}H_{15}N_3S$ requires S, 9.70%); ν_{max} 3425, 3140, 1200, 1160, 1090 cm^{-1} ; and ***N*¹-phenyl-*N*²-(4,6-diphenyl) pyrimidyl-2-thiocarbamide (1k)** m.p. 114° (Found : S, 8.23. $C_{28}H_{18}N_4S$ requires S, 8.37%) were prepared by the above general procedure.

General procedure for the preparation of thiazolidinones :

2-Cyclohexylimino-4-thiazolidinone (2b) : A

mixture of cyclohexylthiourea (1.58 g), monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g), anhydrous sodiumacetate (0.5 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h on a water-bath. The excess ethanol was evaporated and the reaction mixture was poured into cold water. The solid obtained was filtered, washed several times with hot water and crystallised from ethanol, m. p. 120° (Found : S, 15.83. $C_9H_{14}N_2SO$ requires S, 16.16%); ν_{max} 3060-2820 (NH), 1735 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2'-Phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3'-ylimino-4-thiazolidinone (2d) (65%), m.p. 122° (Found : S, 10.23. $C_{16}H_{12}N_4SO$ requires S, 10.12%); and **2-(acridyl-9)ylimino-4-thiazolidinone (2e)** (40%), m.p. 181° (Found : S, 10.86. $C_{16}H_{11}N_3SO$ requires S, 11.30%); ν_{max} 3440 (NH), 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O); **2-phenylimino-3-cyclopentyl-4-thiazolidinone (2f)**, m. p. 92° (Found : S, 12.1. $C_{14}H_{16}N_2SO$ requires S, 12.3%); **2-phenylimino-3-cyclohexyl-4-thiazolidinone (2g)**, m.p. 88° (Found : S, 10.5. $C_{15}H_{18}N_2SO$ requires 11.6%), ν_{max} 2920, 1715 (C=O), 1630 cm^{-1} ; **2-phenylimino-3-cycloheptyl-5-thiazolidinone (2h)**, m.p. 75° (Found : S, 10.8. $C_{16}H_{20}N_2SO$ requires S, 11.1%); **2-(2'-phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3'-ylimino)-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (2i)**, m.p. 120° (Found : S, 8.28. $C_{28}H_{16}N_4SO$ requires S, 8.38%); **2-(acridyl-9)ylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (2j)**, m.p. 170° (Found : S, 8.4. $C_{28}H_{16}N_3SO$ requires S, 8.6%); and **2-(4,6-diphenylpyrimido)ylimino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (2k)**, m.p. 132° (Found : S, 7.30. $C_{28}H_{18}N_4SO$ requires S, 7.58%) were prepared by the above procedure.

3-Cyclohexylimino-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone (3b ; R'=C₆H₅) A mixture of cyclohexylthiazolidinone (1.98 g, 0.01M), benzaldehyde (1.06 g, 0.01M) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture after cooling was poured into crushed ice. The pale yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed with hot water, dried and crystallised (40%), m.p. 242° (Found : S, 10.8. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2SO$ requires S, 11.1%); ν_{max} 2920-2840 (NH), 1685 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2-(2'-Phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3'-ylimino)-5-bromo-5-(α -bromo)-benzyl-4-thiazolidinone (4i) : A solution of 2-(2'-phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridin-3'-ylimino)-5-benzal-4-thiazolidinone (0.001 M) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was treated with bromine (0.001 M) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) by dropwise addition at 0° and kept overnight. The yellow solid separated was filtered, washed with ether and dried (50%), m.p. 206° (Found : Br, 29.0. $C_{28}H_{15}N_4OSBr_2$ requires Br, 29.09%).

2-(2'-Phenylimidazo[1,2-a]pyridylimino-3')-5-sulphonamido-phenyldiazo-4-thiazolidinone (5i) : Sulphanilamide (0.5 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and water (25 ml) was diazotised with HNO_2 (0.25 g $NaNO_2$ in 30 ml water) in an ice-bath. The resulting diazo solution was added gradually with stirring to a previously cooled solution of thiazolidinone (0.65 g) in NaOH (0.5 g in 20 ml water) kept in an ice-bath. After the mixture was stirred

for 0.5 h a deep red coloured azo dye was separated out. It was crystallised from ethanol (50%), m.p. 172° (Found : S, 13 ; N, 19.87. C₂₂H₁₇N₇S₂O₃ requires S, 13.03 ; N, 19.95%). The physical and analytical data of benzylidene-thiazolidinones, their dibromides and sulphonamido derivatives have been shown in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of thiazolidinone 2f: A mixture of the thiazolidinone (0.5 g) in rectified spirit (25 ml) and concentrated HCl (6 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8 h. Excess of alcohol was distilled off and the residue extracted with boiling water. The water insoluble component corresponding to 3-cyclopentyl-2,4-thiazolidione gave m.p. 166-67° (Found : S, 17.03. C₈H₁₁NSO₂ requires S, 17.29%).

The aqueous solution was basified by dilute NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The evaporation of ether left an oily mass corresponding to aniline.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF BENZYLIDENE DIBROMIDE AND SULPHONAMIDO DERIVATIVES

Compd.	Benzylidene (3)		Dibromide (4)		Sulphonamido (5)	
	M.p. °C	S % : Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	Br % : Found/ (Calcd.)	M.p. °C	S % : Found/ (Calcd.)
d	>250	800 (8.08)	206	29.00 (29.09)	172	13.00 (13.03)
e	230	7.50 (8.30)	—	—	—	—
f	124	8.50 (9.10)	239	37.42 (37.38)	195	21.50 (21.71)
g	165	8.52 (8.83)	240	36.01 (36.18)	212	21.10 (21.05)
h	184	8.23 (8.51)	>250	35.16 (35.09)	240	20.28 (20.42)
i	224	6.52 (6.77)	152	24.32 (24.53)	—	—
j	118	6.82 (7.00)	253	—	—	—
k	187	6.10 (6.27)	>250	—	—	—

Hydrolysis of 2g and 2h gave 3-cyclohexyl-2,4-thiazolidione (m.p. 164°) and 3-cycloheptyl-2,4-thiazolidione (m.p. 159°), respectively along with aniline. On the other hand the hydrolysis of 2i, 2j and 2k furnished imidazopyrimidoamine, 9-aminoacridine and diphenylaminopyrimidine, respectively. 3-Phenyl-2,4-thiazolidione, m.p. 201° (lit.⁴ 200-201°) was also obtained along with the amines.

3-Cyclohexylimino-5-dimethylaminomethyl-4-thiazolidinone (6b): A mixture of 2b (0.5 g) and dimethylamine (1 ml) in dilute HCl (5 ml) was refluxed gently during which formalin (1 ml) was added dropwise. After a period of 2 h it was cooled and the separated precipitate was basified with ammonia and kept overnight. The solid obtained was washed with water and dried (40%), m.p. 125° (Found : S, 10.21. C₁₇H₂₂N₃SO requires S, 10.09%). 6f (m.p. 144°) and 6g (m.p. 154°) were prepared from 3f and 2g, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for providing a fellowship to one of them (J.S.).

References

- P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY, A. NAYAK and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 680 ; P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 931, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *Curr. Sci.*, 1972, 41, 539 ; P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, 13, 753.
- G. R. NEWKOME and A. NAYAK, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1979, 25, 83.
- J. SAHU, T. K. SAHU, S. K. NAIK and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, in the press.
- T. E. ACHARY, P. N. DHAL and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1204.
- R. R. ASTIK and K. A. THAKAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 1013.
- A. ALBERT and B. RITCHIE, *Org. Synth.*, 3, 53.

Synthesis of 5-Methoxy-1,3-disubstituted-benzimidazolin-2-thiones as Potential Biologically Active Agents†

RAJENDRA S. VARMA* and VIJAY A. SINGH

Department of Chemistry
and

HIRDAY N. VERMA and SUDHAKAR D. DWIVEDI

Plant Virus Laboratory, Department of Botany, Lucknow
University, Lucknow-226 007

*Manuscript received 4 October 1983, revised 4 April 1984,
accepted 15 August 1984*

BENZIMIDAZOLES have been reported to possess wide range of biological activity, such as antibacterial¹, antifungal², anthelmintic^{3,4}, antiviral activity^{5,6}. 5-Methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thione (I) as well as cyclised products from I also exhibited antibacterial activity⁷. In consideration of these observations the synthesis of the title compounds and their evaluation as antiviral agents against *Sunnehmp rosette* virus has been undertaken.

The synthesis of 5-methoxybenzimidazolin-2-thione (I)⁸ was achieved by the reaction of 4-methoxy-*o*-phenylenediamine^{10,11} and CS₂ in presence of ethanolic KOH. The title compounds were synthesised from I by reacting it with 40% aqueous formaldehyde solution and various amines under the condition of Mannich reaction. I was also acylated to get 1,3-diacetyl-5-methoxy-benzimidazolin-2-thione (3).

The ir spectrum of 2a showed characteristic bands at 2820 (CH₂), 1220 (C=S) and 1110 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). Its nmr spectrum was in accord with assigned structures. Peaks (δ) were observed at 2.6-2.7 (8H, -CH₂-O-CH₂), 3.5-3.6 (8H-N<CH₂),

†Part XLV of the series "Potential Biologically Active Agents".